

Supplementary Figure S9. Growth curves of WT (green circle), $\Delta aceE$ (dark grey square), $\Delta aceF$ (grey triangle) and $\Delta pflA$ (light grey inverted triangle) in M9 0.3% acetate. Data represent the average and SEM for three independent biological replicates.